

FACTORS AFFECTING THE CHOICE OF BANKS IN BANGLADESH

A. T. M. Jakaria Khan *
Chowdhury Asim Mahmud Bin Harun **
Nusrat Jahan ***

Abstract

With the entrance of more than 10 new banks in the last decade, the number of scheduled banks in Bangladesh now stands at 60, generating a lot of competition. Keeping in mind the importance of attracting customers in this highly competitive industry, this paper investigates the specific factors that affect the choice of banks amongst the customers in the banking industry of Bangladesh. The data was gathered through questionnaire from a sample of 254 respondents. One-Sample T-test and Independent Sample T-test were conducted for data analysis. The results of the study showed that Service Features, Security System and availability of ATM services were the top 3 factors considered by the customers in choosing a bank, while whether the bank is following any religious principle does not play any role in the choice of banks. It was also found that compared to male customers, female customers give more importance to Product Variety, Rates and Charges of the banking products and services, and Recommendation while choosing a bank. The study recommends that the banks of Bangladesh give due attention to these factors to improve their competitiveness and profitability.

Keywords : Banking Industry of Bangladesh, Banks in Bangladesh, Choice of Banks.

1. INTRODUCTION

The banking industry of Bangladesh started its journey with a total of 18 bank right after the independence. At that time, the banks were either state-owned or foreign banks. In the 1980s, private commercial banks started entering the industry, and after the licensing of more than 10 new banks in the last decade, the number of scheduled banks in Bangladesh currently stands at 60. This large number and frequent entrance of new banks has made this industry a highly competitive one, where customer acquisition has become very challenging. This makes it important to understand what drives the customers' choice of banks. This study focuses on the existing and potential customers of the banking sector of Bangladesh to determine what factors customers consider while choosing a bank.

The paper develops as follows. First, the literature review explores the bank selection criteria that have been investigated throughout the world, followed by a discussion of some influences on bank selection based only on Asian countries, finally looking at similar studies conducted in Bangladesh. Based on this, probable factors are

* Assistant Professor, Institute of Business Administration (IBA), University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

** Undergraduate Student, Institute of Business Administration (IBA), University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

*** Graduate, Institute of Business Administration (IBA), University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

identified. Next, the data collection and analysis method is described. The findings are then presented along with their interpretation. Finally, there is a discussion on the results and their possible implications.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various scholars from different countries all around the world have conducted empirical studies using different approaches on the factors that drive customers' selection of banks. In USA, a study conducted by Anderson et al. (1976) established that customers focus on *friends' recommendations, reputation of the bank, availability of credit, friendliness of staff and service charges on accounts* as the most important selection criteria. This was criticized by Laroche (1986) as this study did not find *location* or *convenience* to be an important criterion as found in previous studies. *Convenience* was identified as an important factor in later studies conducted by Gerrard and Cunningham (2001) and Lee and Marlowe (2003). However, later studies by Kaynak (1995), Ta and Har (2000), Al-Mossawi (2001) and recently by Rao (2010) all found recommendation, by either family or friends or peers, to be the most significant factor, as suggested by Anderson et al. (1976).

Using Analytic Hierarchy Process, Javalgi et al. (1989) conducted a study which concluded that *safety of fund, availability of loans and interest rate on savings account* were the factors considered to be most important by the customers. Kazeh and Decker (1993) in their research on college students of Maryland, USA found *service charges, reputation, interest charged on loans, quick loan approval, and friendly tellers* to be significant in selecting a bank. Boyd et al. (1994) studying the opinions of customers from age group under 21 years found *bank's reputation* to be most important decision criterion, supplemented by other factors such as *location, hours of operation, interest on savings accounts and the provision of convenient and quick services*.

In Finland, Holstius et al. (1995) found that the most influential factors considered by customers were - *location near home or work, fast and efficient service, recommendations of friends and relatives, external appearance, interior comfort of the bank counter partitions and mass media advertising of the services*. In Poland, research carried out by Kennington et al. (1996) found variations of similar factors such as *reputation, price/cost, convenience and service* to be emphasized upon by the existing and potential customers.

A study (Edris, 1997) conducted on the Kuwaiti customers indicated that *size of bank assets, efficiency of personnel help in financial emergencies, banking experience, friendliness of staff, reputation, communications with staff, knowledge of firm's business, prompt provision of services, and availability of branches abroad* were the contributing factors in selection of a bank. Similar study (Owusu-Frimpong, 1999) in Ghana conducted on the customers' behavior led to the discovery that *convenient location, friendly employees and size of the bank* were the factors that contributed most in determination of bank selection decision.

Looking in to Asia, it is seen that there have been scientific studies in this area but they focused more on variation among samples, like disparity in factors between multiple and single bank users (Mokhlis & Salleh, 2009), impact of gender in choice of banks (Mokhlis S., 2009) and lastly how choice of bank varies among cultural groups based in Malaysia (Mokhlis, Mat, & Salleh, 2010). In terms of Religion, it was seen that Muslims preferred banks with *speedy transactions, friendly bank employees, efficient and quick service, and confidentiality* whereas, non-Muslims preferred banks with *friendly bank employees, efficient and quick service, high reputation and image, and speedy transactions* (Haron et al., 1994).

In Malaysia, eight important factors were identified, namely- *recommendation, convenience, branding, rate charges, flexibility in accounts, papers required, variation in offerings, rates offered, and friendly environment* by Kumar et al. (2009). Next, a study using 750 respondents of four regions in Malaysia was conducted by Dusuki (2007) which identified *friendly employees, size, profit mindedness, convenience, and slow but efficient service* as significant determinants in choice of banks. The data was analyzed using Friedman Test.

Islamic banking customers of Afghanistan were studied by Farooq et al. (2010). They found that the most important factors for selection of Islamic banking products were- *recommendation of family and friends, easy access to branch, profitability of the bank and religious inclination*. Analytical hierarchy process was used by Ta and Har (2000) with a dataset containing Singaporean respondents to access prime decision factors. The results of the evaluation stated that *convenient location, recommendations, high interest rate, self-banking facilities, low charges, undergraduate privileges, quality of service, long operating hours and low-loan rates* were the determining factors in choice of banks.

1000 university students of Bahrain were studied to investigate influential factors by Al-Mossawi (2001). The findings found the following to be most influential factors - *availability of parking space, location and availability of ATMs, reputation, friendliness*. Interestingly, Al-Mossawi went on to recommend that there is gender bias and hence male and female customers should be targeted using different strategies.

Moving into sub-continent, again student banking was given importance by Rao (2010) and his research concluded that *brand name, security system, low charges, parking facility, loyalty programs, employee courtesy, reasonable rate of interest, zero balance account, and speedy services* were significant in choosing a bank. In Pakistan, Rehman and Ahmed (2008) found that convenience, online banking, overall environment, and customer service were the most important factors.

Now coming into Bangladesh, a study was conducted by Siddique (2012) using Nationalized Commercial Banks (NCBs) and Private Commercial Banks (PCBs) of Rajshahi to explore the factors in choosing bank accounts. A total of 600 respondents were used to conclude that *bank management, effective and efficient customer*

services, online banking, image of the bank, and speed and quality of services were the most important factors for PCBs. Compared to this, the customers of NCBs wanted *convenient branch location, safe investment, low service charges, low interest rates on loan, and a variety of services offered*. Rashid and Hassan (2009) conducted a similar study but they focused on the Islamic banks only. Parvin and Parveen (2012), using a survey data of 206 respondents, found that *ease of opening account* was the most important variable. They also observed that responsiveness was the most important factor to customers which included *personality, foreign exchange service, counseling, and friendliness*. Other services like - *merchant banking, electronic fund transfer service, cash management service, convenience, and safety factors* were also of quite high importance. Siddiqi (2011), Fatima and Razzaque (2013), Karim and Chowdhury (2014) all conducted separate studies focusing on service quality as the defining factor to determine customer satisfaction.

Among these prior works in Bangladesh, Siddique (2012) considered only three PCBs and NCBs and focused on only the Rajshahi district of Bangladesh. Most of the banks and their customers have remained untouched from his study. Moreover, the author did not consider any Islamic bank in his study, whereas Rashid and Hassan (2009) focused on the Islamic banks only. Consequently, it would not be worthy to generalize the findings of the paper in a broad aspect. Siddiqi (2011), Fatima and Razzaque (2013), Karim and Chowdhury (2014) all used servqual model to determine customer satisfaction, which leaves the selection criteria out of the study. Demographic factors such as gender or age has not been considered in any of these previous studies. So, this broad area is yet to be explored in Bangladesh.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The broad objective of this research is to determine what factors affect the customers' selection of banks, focusing on the banking sector of Bangladesh. The specific objectives of the study are:

- To identify the factors affecting the choice of banks
- To determine whether gender plays any significant role in determining these aforementioned factors
- To make recommendation on what the banks should focus on for attracting customers

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Target Population and Sample Size

Population of this study is the existing and potential customers of the banking sector of Bangladesh. Data was collected from August 2019 to September 2019. An online survey was conducted, where the questionnaire was posted in various online platforms for collecting responses. Using non-probabilistic convenience judgmental sampling technique, a total of 254 responses were collected.

4.2 Data and Data Collection Technique

This study has used both primary and secondary data. Secondary data have been analyzed to develop a framework for the study and primary data have been used to conduct the research. Primary data have been collected through a structured questionnaire containing questions seeking demographic information of respondents and their perception about the factors influencing their choice of banks. Information about respondents' perceptions about the factors was collected through the 4-point Likert Scale. In the scale, the selection of answers ranging from 4 to 1 indicated very important, important, neutral and not important respectively.

4.3 Analytical Techniques

For the purpose of in-depth analysis, One-Sample T-test and Independent Samples T-test were conducted using SPSS (Version: 19).

4.4 Hypotheses

For the purpose of the study, total 30 hypotheses have been developed and tested. 15 hypotheses are tested using One-Sample T-test and 15 hypotheses are tested using Independent Samples T-test. The hypotheses developed in this regard are in the next section.

5. RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

5.1 Descriptive Statistics

The demographic profile of the respondents is summarized in the following table:

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	196	77.2
	Female	58	22.8
	Total	254	100
Age	20-29 years	134	52.8
	30-39 years	107	42.1
	40-49 years	10	3.9
	50-59 years	3	1.2
	Total	254	100

Table 1 shows that majority of the respondents are male (77.2%) and only 22.8% of the respondents are female. Also, the age level of 52.8% of the respondents is between 20 to 29 years, 42.1% between 30 to 39 years, only 3.9% and 1.2% between 40 to 49 years and 50 to 59 years respectively.

The survey response on the specific factors is summarized in Table 2. It shows that more than 80% of the respondents perceive product feature, service feature, rates &

charges, bank’s reputation, ATM availability, branch location, and security system as important criteria in choosing a bank whereas a rate of more than 50% of the respondents also consider product variety, recommendation, having a known person working for the bank, process simplicity, and asset quality of the bank to be somewhat important factors in this regard. However, more than 70% of the respondents think that advertisement, religious view, and parking facility are not important or do not make any difference in the choice of banks.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Different Variables Related to Bank Selection

Factor	Not Important		Neutral		Important		Very Important	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Product variety	37	14.6	66	26.0	107	42.1	44	17.3
Product feature	11	4.3	28	11.0	110	43.3	105	41.3
Service feature	4	1.6	6	2.4	89	35.0	155	61.0
Rates & charges	13	5.1	28	11.0	97	38.2	116	45.7
Bank’s reputation	8	3.1	21	8.3	110	43.3	115	45.3
Advertisement	106	41.7	104	40.9	37	14.6	7	2.8
Recommendation	35	14.2	74	29.1	105	41.3	39	15.4
Known person	51	20.1	72	28.3	88	34.6	43	16.9
Religious view	109	42.9	81	31.9	28	11.0	36	14.2
ATM availability	7	2.8	19	7.5	107	42.1	121	47.6
Branch location	8	3.1	29	11.4	108	42.5	109	42.9
Parking facility	108	42.5	95	37.4	38	15.0	13	5.1
Process simplicity	19	7.5	42	16.5	114	44.9	79	31.1
Security system	4	1.6	17	6.7	78	30.7	155	61.0
Asset quality of the bank	33	13.0	74	29.1	86	33.9	61	24.0

5.2 One-Sample T-test

The study sought to determine which criteria are perceived to be important in making the decision of choosing a bank. For this purpose, several hypotheses have been developed and tested using One-Sample T-test. The test value was set to 2.5 (the mean value of the scales 1 to 4) which indicates neutral role of a feature in the decision-making process. The test was conducted with 95% Confidence Interval. The hypotheses developed in this regard are as follows:

Hypothesis 1:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about the product variety offered by banks

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about the product variety offered by banks

Hypothesis 2:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about the product features offered by banks

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about the product features offered by banks

Hypothesis 3:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about the service features offered by banks

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about the service features offered by banks

Hypothesis 4:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about the rates & charges of banks

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about the rates & charges of banks

Hypothesis 5:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about the bank's reputation

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about the bank's reputation

Hypothesis 6:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about advertisement on different media

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about advertisement on different media

Hypothesis 7:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about recommendation by family members, friends and relatives about the bank

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about recommendation by family members, friends and relatives about the bank

Hypothesis 8:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about the existence of known person in the bank

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about the existence of known person in the bank

Hypothesis 9:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about the bank being in-line with religious principles

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about the bank being in-line with religious principles

Hypothesis 10:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about availability of ATMs

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about availability of ATMs

Hypothesis 11:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about branch location of banks

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about branch location of banks

Hypothesis 12:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about parking facility

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about parking facility

Hypothesis 13:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about process simplicity of banks

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about process simplicity of banks

Hypothesis 14:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about the security system of banks

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about the security system of banks

Hypothesis 15:

H_0 : Customers have a neutral perception about the asset quality of banks

H_A : Customers do not have a neutral perception about the asset quality of banks

Table 3: Result of One-sample T-test

Hypothesis No.	Mean	SD	T	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision at $\alpha = 5\%$
1	2.62	0.936	2.078	0.039	Reject the null hypothesis
2	3.22	0.808	14.14	0	Reject the null hypothesis
3	3.56	0.625	26.92	0	Reject the null hypothesis
4	3.24	0.846	14.03	0	Reject the null hypothesis
5	3.31	0.755	17.05	0	Reject the null hypothesis
6	1.78	0.793	-14.4	0	Reject the null hypothesis
7	2.58	0.915	1.371	0.172	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
8	2.48	0.997	-0.252	0.801	Cannot reject the null hypothesis

Hypothesis No.	Mean	SD	T	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision at $\alpha = 5\%$
9	1.96	1.053	-8.102	0	Reject the null hypothesis
10	3.35	0.737	18.3	0	Reject the null hypothesis
11	3.25	0.78	15.37	0	Reject the null hypothesis
12	1.83	0.867	-12.37	0	Reject the null hypothesis
13	3.00	0.882	8.96	0	Reject the null hypothesis
14	3.51	0.693	23.27	0	Reject the null hypothesis
15	2.69	0.979	3.077	0.002	Reject the null hypothesis

The results on table 3 show that only in case of the **recommendation** and **known person**, the p-values (0.172 and 0.801 respectively) are greater than 0.05. This suggests that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected which, in turn, indicates that the recommendation and having a known person working in the bank do not make any difference in the choice. The result directly contradicts the studies conducted by Anderson et al. (1976), Kaynak (1995), Ta and Har (2000), Al-Mossawi (2001) and recently by Rao (2010) who all found recommendation, by either family or friends or peers, to be the most significant factor. One explanation can be that in this era of technological advancement and social media proliferation, one can easily find out relevant information about the banks online, which may not have been possible previously, leading to a decrease of the importance of recommendation of friends and family.

Product feature, service feature, rates & charges, bank's reputation, ATM availability, branch location, process simplicity, and security system are clearly the most important factors having means ranging from 3.00 to 3.56. In addition, product variety and asset quality of bank have means 2.62 and 2.69 respectively. Although these values are not substantially larger than 2, these features seem to have a fairly mild influence in the selection of bank.

Finally, the results indicate that customers do not perceive advertisement, religious view, and parking facility much important while selecting a bank. So, the top 3 factors while choosing a bank are Service Feature, Security System and ATM Availability.

5.3 Independent Samples T-Test

The study tried to determine whether customers' perception about different criteria differs based on their gender. For this purpose, several hypotheses have been developed and tested using Independent Samples T-test. The test was conducted with 95% Confidence Interval. The hypotheses developed in this regard are as follows:

Hypothesis 1:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about the product variety offered by banks are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about the product variety offered by banks are different for their genders

Hypothesis 2:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about the product features offered by banks are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about the product features offered by banks are different for their genders

Hypothesis 3:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about the service features offered by banks are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about the service features offered by banks are different for their genders

Hypothesis 4:

H_0 : Customers' perception about the rates & charges of banks are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about the rates & charges of banks are different for their genders

Hypothesis 5:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about the bank's reputation are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about the bank's reputation are different for their genders

Hypothesis 6:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about advertisement on different media are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about advertisement on different media are different for their genders

Hypothesis 7:

H_0 : Customers' perception about recommendation by family members, friends and relatives about the bank are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about recommendation by family members, friends and relatives about the bank are different for their genders

Hypothesis 8:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about the existence of known person in the bank are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about the existence of known person in the bank are different for their genders

Hypothesis 9:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about the bank being in-line with religious principles are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about the bank being in-line with religious principles are different for their genders

Hypothesis 10:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about availability of ATMs are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about availability of ATMs are different for their genders

Hypothesis 11:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about branch location of banks are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about branch location of banks are different for their genders

Hypothesis 12:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about parking facility are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about parking facility are different for their genders

Hypothesis 13:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about process simplicity of banks are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about process simplicity of banks are different for their genders

Hypothesis 14:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about the security system of banks are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about the security system of banks are different for their genders

Hypothesis 15:

H_0 : Customers' perceptions about the asset quality of banks are indifferent of their genders

H_A : Customers' perceptions about the asset quality of bank are different for their genders

Table 4 : Result of Independent Sample T-test

Hypothesis No.	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision at $\alpha = 5\%$
1	-3.186	0.002	-0.378	0.119	Reject the null hypothesis
2	-0.451	0.652	-0.055	0.121	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
3	0.286	0.775	0.027	0.094	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
4	-2.472	0.014	-0.309	0.125	Reject the null hypothesis
5	-1.028	0.305	-0.116	0.113	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
6	-0.859	0.391	-0.102	0.119	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
7	-2.359	0.02	-0.3	0.127	Reject the null hypothesis
8	0.612	0.541	0.091	0.149	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
9	-0.433	0.665	-0.068	0.158	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
10	-1.198	0.232	-0.132	0.11	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
11	-1.032	0.303	-0.12	0.117	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
12	-1.042	0.298	-0.135	0.13	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
13	-0.039	0.969	-0.005	0.132	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
14	-1.147	0.252	-0.119	0.104	Cannot reject the null hypothesis
15	-1.537	0.126	-0.224	0.146	Cannot reject the null hypothesis

For hypotheses 1 and 7, Levene's test for equality of variance produced significance 0.0 and 0.011 respectively, which are less than 0.05. As a result, equal variance is not assumed in case of these hypotheses, and corresponding df value has been considered. For all other hypotheses, df value is 252.

The results on table 4 suggest that there is no significant difference between importance given to any particular feature based on the gender of the respondents except for three features - product variety, rates & charges, and recommendation.

There was a significant difference in mean importance given to product variety by males and females ($t_{122,397} = -3.186, p = 0.002$). Specifically, product variety is more important to female respondents ($M = 2.91, SD = 0.732$) than to male respondents ($M = 2.54, SD = 0.973$). The reason for this could be that female are more interested in diversifying their investment portfolio and hence to them variety is more important. They do not want to invest in same type of schemes.

Similarly, it was found that there was a significant difference in mean importance given to rates & charges by males and females ($t_{252} = -2.472, p = 0.014$). Results show that rates & charges are more important to female respondents ($M = 3.48, SD = 0.707$) than to male respondents ($M = 3.17, SD = 0.871$). This can be attributed to the fact that females have a higher opportunity cost and so they are very cautious when borrowing as well as saving.

Finally, the results indicate that there was a significant difference in mean importance given to recommendation by males and females ($t_{103,590} = -2.359, p = 0.02$). It indicates that recommendations are more important to female respondents ($M = 2.81, SD = 0.826$) than to male respondents ($M = 2.51, SD = 0.931$). The reason for this could be that females want to avoid bad experience caused by negative personal interaction at the bank, so they only go to banks recommended by others.

Finally, the study arrived at conclusion that product variety, rates & charges, and recommendation play a more important role in the decision-making process for female customers than for male customers. The other features show negligible difference when gender of customers is considered.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

The study found that Service feature, Security system and ATM availability are the three most important factors while choosing a bank in Bangladesh. These are closely followed by Bank's reputation, Branch location, Rates & charges and Product feature as important criteria. This indicates that most people in Bangladesh give much more importance to the basic features of the core product (rates, offerings) rather than the augmented product (parking facilities, asset quality). So, banks should focus more on improving their basic product.

Although a significant number of studies conducted previously found recommendation by friends or family members to be one of the most important factors while choosing a bank, this study found recommendation and having a known person in the bank are not given much importance. Hence, banks may need to rethink about their strategy of creating brand image and establishing relationships with customers. Also, some banks have invested extensively in BTL marketing. However, from the study it can be seen

that advertisement is seldom important to potential or existing customers. So, banks should do proper cost-benefit analysis before making investment in advertisement.

The study also revealed that female customers are more interested in product variety and rates & charges compared to male customers, which supports the current practices in the industry to customize banking products for targeting female customers. Moreover, as the recommendations factor is found to still play a role in reaching more female customers, as it is more important to them than the male customers, the banks should put in efforts to ensure positive word-of-mouth to their female customers.

This research has focused mostly on identifying the factors that play important role in customers' selection of banks. In addition, it has also looked into the implication of customers' gender on these factors. Other demographic factors such as age, income, education were beyond the scope of this study and further research is recommended on this topic. Nevertheless, this study should serve as a reference point for managers, policymakers, and investors involved in the banking industry of Bangladesh.

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